

Exploring English-Majored Students' Academic Stress and Coping Strategies: A Mix Method Research at A Private University

Truong Dinh Minh Dang

Faculty of Foreign Languages, Nguyen Tat Thanh University, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam.

ABSTRACT: Academic stress has long been a subject of interest among researchers. University students often face significant levels of stress due to a variety of stressors. This study aims to (1) examine the prevalence of stress and the factors contributing to it, and (2) explore students' views on stress and their coping strategies among undergraduate English studies students. A survey was conducted with a randomly selected sample of 125 students from a private university, using a questionnaire. The questionnaire addressed both academic and non-academic factors, revealing an average stress level of 2.72. Female English studies students reported a slightly higher stress level compared to their male counterparts. The findings revealed that, among academic stressors, fear of failure was the primary contributor, while limited time for recreation and homesickness were identified as the main non-academic stressors. The second data is derived from a case study design with semi-structured interview with 12 English-majored university students at the private university. The results identify 3 main coping strategies used by students when facing school stress: (1) evasion, (2) diversion, and (3) resolution. These findings highlight the critical importance of teaching about stress and coping strategies in health and life skills education.

KEYWORDS: Academic stress, Coping strategies, English-majored students, Students' perspectives, Stress factors

INTRODUCTION

Studying English can be highly demanding, placing considerable strain on students' mental health. Stress is a psychological response that emerges from the interaction between an individual and an environment perceived as threatening to their well-being, acting as an external force that impacts both mental and physical health. Language studies, particularly in English, are noted for having a higher prevalence of stress compared to other fields. Research indicates that students majoring in English often experience heightened stress levels throughout their undergraduate years, primarily due to the demanding curriculum and the language proficiency standards they must achieve. This research aims to investigate the academic stress encountered by English majors at the University and to identify the coping strategies they utilize to manage this stress. Understanding the factors that contribute to academic stress and how students cope is essential for enhancing their well-being and academic success. This study is driven by the need to address a gap in the literature concerning the specific stressors faced by English majors in Vietnam. While many studies have examined academic stress in general, few have specifically targeted this demographic. The research seeks to pinpoint the situations that induce stress in the lives of English major students and aims to evaluate the prevalence of stress and the contributing factors among undergraduate linguistics students, as well as to explore gender differences within the university context. The overall increase in school-related stress can be contextualized within the growing importance of educational qualifications for job opportunities in today's knowledge-based economies (Högberg, 2021; Högberg & Strandh, 2024; Krogh & Madsen, 2023; Pascoe et al., 2020). Knowledge is seen as a vital element in boosting economic productivity, and national education systems are working hard to remain competitive in the global knowledge economy (Hilt et al., 2024). This paper also aims to delve into the students' perspectives and the coping strategies they employ to handle school-related stress.

(1) **What are the factors causing academic stress for English-majored students?**

(2) **What are the students' coping strategies used to manage school-related stress?**

By exploring these questions, the research seeks to illuminate the specific sources of academic stress faced by students majoring in English, as well as their perceptions and coping mechanisms regarding these challenges. This study's results may be discussed with the increasing literature on academic stress and mental health in higher education, particularly within English language studies. In addition, this research could provide valuable insights for educators, academic advisors, and university administrators to assist in

the creation of supportive systems and programs for stress management unique to English majors. The purpose of this study also is to help students learn how to deal with academic stress so as to enable students to foster their well-being and academic achievement.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Stress and Stress factors

Stress is a response that encompasses both psychological and physiological aspects, arising from internal and external pressures that challenge a person's ability to cope. It has been widely examined in areas such as psychology, education, and linguistics because of its profound impact on mental health, academic success, and overall well-being.

Typically, stress is viewed as a state of mental or emotional strain that is triggered by difficult or demanding situations (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). The transactional model of stress introduced by Lazarus and Folkman emphasizes that stress results from the interaction between individuals and their surroundings, occurring when perceived demands surpass the resources available to them. Stress can manifest in various forms, including emotional, physical, and behavioral symptoms, and can be classified as either acute or chronic based on the duration and intensity of the stressors.

Stress in Educational Contexts

Educational settings are frequently identified as high-stress environments, particularly for students navigating the demands of academic life. Academic stress refers to the mental distress associated with anticipated academic challenges, such as exams, assignments, and competitive environments (Misra & McKean, 2000). It is recognized as a significant factor affecting students' cognitive functioning, emotional regulation, and physical health.

Academic stress among students has been widely studied, with researchers identifying key stressors such as excessive assignments, competition with peers, failure, and strained relationships with fellow students or lecturers (Fairbrother & Warn, 2003). University students' academic performance is commonly assessed through their success or failure in course units, the number of courses completed or failed (Goldfinch & Hughes, 2007), and their grades, often reflected in their Grade Point Average (GPA) or Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA) (Bernold, Spurlin, & Anson, 2007). Baker (2003) emphasized that undergraduates encounter new interpersonal, social, and academic challenges when transitioning from secondary school to university, which can be stressful. Immediate challenges include career decision-making, forming new relationships, adapting to unfamiliar ideas that challenge prior beliefs, and adjusting to living away from home (Lumley & Provenzano, 2003). Baker emphasizes that the success of this adjustment largely depends on a student's ability to cope with stress, which subsequently influences their academic motivation and performance. DeBerard, Spielmans, and Julka (2004) propose that social support from friends, peers, and religious communities serves as a protective factor, assisting students in managing stress during this transitional phase. In academic environments, stress commonly stems from high expectations, information overload, academic pressure, unrealistic goals, limited opportunities, and intense competition, all of which contribute to anxiety, fear, and tension among students (Sinha, Sharma, & Nepal, 2001). Dahlin, Joneborg, and Runeson (2005) found that undergraduate students experience the highest levels of study-related pressure. Likewise, research by Misra, McKean, West, and Russo (2000) identified the pressure of meeting assessment deadlines as a significant source of stress for students. Academic stress is often associated with exam preparation, competition for grades, and the challenge of absorbing large amounts of material within a limited time (Kohn & Frazer, 1986). The imbalance between course load and available time is another factor contributing to academic stress (Zeidner, 1992). Studies indicate that first-year students often view their coursework as demanding, and this perception is linked to heightened exam-related stress (Mani, 2010). Talib and Zai-ur-Rehman (2012) found that 53% of students identified course load as a major stressor, which negatively impacted their GPA. Additionally, students report that the pressure to review all material before exams is stressful, and while the exam itself may not be the direct cause of stress, the potential impact on their academic and professional future is a significant concern (Mani, 2010).

Stress Factors in Educational Contexts

Stress is part and parcel of education; caused by a combination of academic, social and personal pressures. Students face anxiety and pressure that arises from performance demands, tight deadlines, and the need to manage extracurricular commitments, and these challenges become more pronounced in a setting characterized by high expectations and fierce competition.

The advancement of technology into education brought new stressor, making students digitally literate and comfortable with online learning successes. This is true especially for students studying languages, who may experience unique challenges specific to language acquisition, as well as cultural transition challenges and technical skill acquisition relevant to their field.

Such stressors can manifest themselves in decreased academic performance, poor mental health, and physical ailments, among other things. However, how individuals experience and manage stress can vary based on factors like resilience, social support, and available resources. Understanding the root causes of stress and its contributing factors is essential for creating effective strategies to reduce its impact and help students reach their academic and personal aspirations.

Coping strategies

Problem-focused and emotion-focused coping strategies was classified as two main types of coping strategies by Lazarus and Folkman (1984). Problem focused approach: These strategies seek to deal with and modify the stressor indicating it is usually applied when people feel that they can affect/change the situation. Such strategies can include confronting the stressor itself, creating a plan or asking for assistance. In contrast, emotion-focussed strategies aim to cope with emotional reactions, and are usually used when the stressor is perceived to be immutable. Such approaches may involve relaxation, venting feelings or social support (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984; Perzow et al., 2021). Avoidance-oriented coping also includes distancing from the stressor, either physically or mentally and can take form as ignoring or distraction (Carver et al., 1989). While these categories offer a useful framework for understanding coping, they also have limitations (Saha et al., 2014).

Recent research attests to a more flexible way of coping, understanding that individuals often combine strategies differently based on the context at hand, their properties, and the resources available (Skinner et al., 2003; Cheng et al., 2014). Coping flexibility, which is moving from one coping strategy to another depending on which one works in that given situation (Kato, 2012), is associated with better mental health outcomes (Aldao et al., 2010; Cheng et al., 2014). Coping strategies can impact well-being, and academic performance, but the feasibility of these strategies is often dependent on how well the strategy fits the stressor (Lazarus et al., 1984). Problem-focused coping works somewhat better than emotion-focused coping or avoidance for controllable stressors; however, avoidance at a permanent level may have long-term detrimental effects (Zimmer-Gembeck & Skinner, 2016), especially where controlled domains such as academic success are concerned, where problem-focused tactics fare much better.

Previous Studies

Various researchers pointed out some important issues behind students' academic stress, including academic pressures, social interactions, financial difficulties, everyday life challenges, and family issues (Brougham et al., 2009). These stress factors can immensely deter the students from their mental health and performance, especially under tremendous pressure such as an English language program. Wang et al. (2022) showed the relationship between stress due to studying English and burnout and indicated that self-efficacy and mindfulness together act as major factors regarding the management of stress. Jones, Clarke, and Tharp (2021) identified six major causes of stress among English Departments; these included academic demands, parent-child relationships, peer pressure, financial fears, and personal expectations. Lee et al. (2023) pointed that maladaptive coping strategies can contribute to academic burnout, while adaptive strategies such as seeking social support can help in alleviating the stress. Nguyen et al. (2020) surveyed English majors and found additional stress related to being proficient in the language and performing well academically, with institutional support being critical in relieving it. The works highlight the intricacies of academic stress and that coping strategies such as mindfulness, self-efficacy, and adaptive will help lessen its grip.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study performed both qualitative and quantitative investigations of sources of academic stress, students' perceptions, and the coping strategies they employ. The sample for the investigation was constructed through convenience sampling, allowing students to participate voluntarily. The quantitative data gathered from the respondents looked at description of various kinds of stressors on a Likert scale, which indicated also the frequency of occurrence as presented in a well-constructed questionnaire containing 40 questions. The qualitative insights included responses obtained through semi-structured interviews with open-ended questions, allowing students to express superlative perceptions of personal insights and coping strategies. By amalgamating a structured

formulation of quantitative data with detailed responses provided via qualitative means, the research was able to provide a macro view of the questions asked and an exhaustive analysis of academic stress and coping strategies from different angles.

Setting and Participants

The study was conducted in the English Studies Department at a private university in Ho Chi Minh City, targeting English-majored students. Participants were junior and senior students aged between 20 and 22. English proficiency was not considered in this study, as the level of academic stress was the only focus of assessment. One hundred and twenty-five students participated in the quantitative phase through completion of questionnaires, while 12 students were chosen for the qualitative phase, which consisted of semi-structured interviews. This selection criteria allow diverse perspectives and experiences to emerge from different academic years.

Instruments

To address the first research question, the researcher utilized the Academic Stress Questionnaire created by Rajendran (1990). This questionnaire was initially developed by Kim (1970) and remains widely utilized by researchers such as Gill, Alam & Halder, Hill, Pandey & Shukla, and Porwal & Kumar. Rajendran and Kaliappan later adapted the Students' Academic Stress Scale to suit Indian contexts. It consists of five sections defined by Kim (1970), comprising 40 structured questions: (a) Personal inadequacy (questions 1–8), (b) Fear of failure (questions 9–18), (c) Interpersonal difficulties with teachers (questions 19–24), (d) Teacher-pupil relationship/teaching methodology (questions 25–32), and (e) Inadequate lab or library facilities (questions 33–40). Each item includes five response options: "No Stress," "Slight Stress," "Moderate Stress," "High Stress," and "Extreme Stress." The collected data was categorized into these sections, analyzed, and compared to explore the sources of academic stress among English-major students, focusing on institutional structures, resource limitations, and cultural challenges impacting their academic experiences.

To answer the second research question, the researcher adapted a semi-structured interview guide developed and designed to foster a conversational style (Brinkmann, 2015, Brinkmann & Kvale, 2018), where the participants were encouraged to reflect and elaborate on the interdisciplinary topic. The interview guide touched on the students' experiences with the following three topics "the students' experiences in everyday school life", "stress and coping" and "public health and coping with life". The researcher changed the subject of questions to suit with the participants in this study. The interview featured open-ended questions, such as "How would you describe the experience of being a university student?", "What may be difficult about being an English-majored students?", "How do you usually face with difficulties in school?", "What is stressful for you?", and "What do you usually do to cope with stress in school?".

Ethical issue

This study complies with the ethical principles outlined in the 4th edition of the Ethical Guidelines for Educational Research by the British Educational Research Association. First, approval was granted by the school authorities, and consent forms were provided to all 125 students for questionnaires and 12 students for interviews, detailing the research's objectives, process, and their involvement. Students were assured that their personal information would be kept confidential in both the collected data and the final report, and that their participation would not affect their academic grades. Once all students and their parents provided consent, the experimental phase began. To ensure confidentiality and ease of management, all responses from questionnaires and interviews were assigned numerical labels.

Data Analysis

The data collected from the questionnaires was analyzed statistically through the Mann-Whitney U test and the Kruskal-Wallis test. For better data presentation, the tables were created in Microsoft Excel and Word. For the qualitative data from interviews, recordings were transcribed and analyzed along the thematic analysis framework by Braun and Clarke (2022). Each stage of the analysis involved familiarity with the data, coding, theme identification, developing and refining of themes, and finally naming them. The analysis approach as proposed by Creswell (2007) and Nowell et al. (2017) had allowed for multi-types of data iterative analysis that integrated both types of data into the study.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Research question 1: What are English-majored students’ sources of academic stress?

Among the 125 students who completed the questionnaire, **72.3% were female**, while **27.7% were male**. In terms of background, **36.5% of respondents were from rural areas**, whereas **62.5% were from urban areas**. Table 1 presents a comparison of stress levels between male and female students, analyzed using the **Mann-Whitney U Test**, which assesses differences in mean ranks between two groups. The results indicate that **female students had a higher mean rank than males**. The **p-value of 0.023**, associated with a **Mann-Whitney U score of 3568**, confirms a significant difference, suggesting that **females experience higher stress levels than males**.

Table 1. Academic stress and Gender difference

Factors	Mean	
	Male	Female
Inadequate study facilities	2.72	2.86
Fear of Failure	3.43	3.54
Interpersonal difficulties with teachers	2.76	2.78
Personal Inadequacy	2.89	2.97
Teacher pupil relationship/ Teaching methods	2.67	2.75
Overall	2.89	2.98

The table displays the average scores of stress factors among male and female students, covering five key aspects: inadequate study facilities, fear of failure, difficulties in interacting with teachers, feelings of personal inadequacy, and teacher-student relationships or teaching methods. Fear of failure had the highest mean for both genders (3.43 for males, 3.54 for females). Overall, females reported slightly higher stress levels (2.98) than males (2.89). The smallest gender difference was in interpersonal difficulties with teachers, while the largest was in inadequate study facilities.

Table 2 shows the difference in level of academic stress by educational background area.

Table 2. Academic stress and educational background area difference

Factors	Mean	
	Rural	Urban
Inadequate study facilities	3.15	3.05
Fear of Failure	4.12	3.87
Interpersonal difficulties with teachers	2.86	2.92
Personal Inadequacy	2.87	2.75
Teacher pupil relationship/ Teaching methods	3.21	3.17
Overall	3.24	3.15

The table presents a comparison of academic stress between students from rural and urban educational backgrounds based on various stress-related factors. The mean values indicate that students in rural areas experience slightly higher levels of academic stress overall (3.24) compared to their urban counterparts (3.15). Among the factors, fear of failure has the highest mean score for both groups, with rural students reporting 4.12 and urban students 3.87. Inadequate study facilities and teacher-pupil relationship/teaching methods also contribute significantly to stress, though rural students report slightly higher levels in both cases. Interestingly, interpersonal difficulties with teachers show minimal differences, with urban students (2.92) experiencing slightly more stress than rural students (2.86). Personal inadequacy, on the other hand, is reported higher among rural students (2.87) than urban students (2.75). Overall, while the differences are not drastic, the data suggests that rural students tend to experience marginally higher academic stress across most factors.

This cross-sectional study relied on self-reported data from students, which introduces the possibility of reporting bias. Such bias may have arisen due to respondents' personal interpretation of the questions, a tendency to present their emotions in a particular manner, or inaccuracies in their responses.

Table 3 illustrates the average academic stress factors among students. The results reveal that fear of failure was the most significant stressor. This elevated stress level stemmed from frequent exams, parental notification of progress reports, perceived teacher favoritism, and inadequate teacher-student communication. The mean stress scores ranged from 1.12 to 4.37, indicating that students experienced stress levels ranging from mild to very high. These findings suggest that academic expectations were the primary source of stress from the students' perspective.

Table 3. Academic Stress Factors and Overall Mean

Factors	Items	Mean	Overall Mean
Inadequate study facilities	Lack of concentration during study hours	2.34	2.76
	Conflict with friends/ college authorities	2.56	
	Inadequate space or room for study at home	3.14	
	Lack of assertiveness (confidence) in the class	4.12	
	Lack of opportunity to meet teachers	2.36	
	Lack of mutual help among classmates	2.67	
	Incomplete and confusing study material	1.27	
	Inadequate lab and library facilities	3.58	
Fear of Failure	Progress reports to parents	3.45	3.49
	Worrying about the examinations	4.37	
	Teachers give more punishment in the class	3.78	
	Worry about the results after examinations	2.62	
	Exam papers are tough and not valued well	3.56	
	Unable to complete the assignments in time	4.19	
	Unable to discuss Academic failures with parents	2.87	
	Not able to grasp the subject matter	3.05	
Interpersonal difficulties with teachers	The teacher is not humors towards us.	2.23	2.43
	The teachers do not listen to our ideas.	1.56	
	Biased attitude of the teacher.	3.54	
	Not knowing how to prepare for the examinations.	1.37	
	Lack of communication between teachers and students.	2.09	
	Not enough discussion in the class.	2.86	
	Teachers lacking interest in students	3.06	
Personal Inadequate	Inadequate subject knowledge of the teacher	2.69	2.47
	Difficulties in remembering all that is studied.	1.22	
	Lack of self-confidence	3.12	
	Hesitate to ask the teacher for detailed explanation.	2.96	
	Lack of fluency while speaking the language other than the mother tongue	1.75	
	Difficulty in public speaking	3.45	
	Feeling of inferiority	2.28	
	Eleventh hour preparation for the examinations	1.74	
Difficulty in adjusting with opposite gender	3.27		
	Teachers make too many extra demands on students	3.25	

Teacher-Pupil relationship/ Teaching methods	Poor interest in some subjects	1.12	2.45
	Teachers show socio-economic status on students	2.36	
	Slow in getting along with the curriculum	3.27	
	Monotonous (boring or tedious) teaching style by the teacher.	1.89	
	The teacher is fast and does not use blackboard legibly.	3.58	
	Examination syllabus is too heavy in some subjects.	2.87	
	Importance of the subject matter	1.28	
OVERALL STRESS			2.72

Research question 2: What are the students' coping strategies used to manage school-related stress?

After coding the data, results were identified and categorized into 3 main themes. They are the three key methods used to deal with academic stress by university students.

Evasion

One recurring theme in the material highlights students' passive responses to distress, characterized by a tendency to wait for challenges to resolve themselves without taking proactive steps. Participants shared experiences such as feeling powerless, avoiding engagement, or resigning themselves to their situation. Examples include statements like:

(Participant 1) "I just let things happen and don't try to change them. It feels like there's no point in trying." **(Participant 2)** "When I feel distressed, I often avoid thinking about it. I just wait and hope it goes away on its own."

(Participant 6) "I feel stuck when I'm stressed. Even simple tasks become too hard, and I end up not doing anything."

(Participant 10) "When things pile up, I get overwhelmed. Instead of tackling my work, I find myself procrastinating, losing motivation, and feeling irritated. I don't know how to manage the stress effectively." These responses reflect a passive acceptance of distress, either by ignoring the stressors or waiting for relief to come naturally. Such behavior indicates a lack of active coping strategies, as students appear to let the distress "take control," ultimately leading them to disengage or give up. This pattern aligns with non-productive coping strategies, including avoidance, neglecting the problem, or wishful thinking (Frydenberg & Lewis, 1996). The sense of being overwhelmed by stress further demonstrates that participants feel incapable of managing their situations, highlighting a lack of self-efficacy (Bandura, 2001).

Diversion

Another notable trend was that students experiencing stress tended to distract themselves by engaging in alternative activities. During the interviews, participants discussed replacing negative emotions and feelings of distress through physical activities, redirecting their focus to entertainment such as watching TV or using their phones, or finding solace in social interactions. They mentioned that exercising or spending time outdoors helped them release pent-up emotions, while talking to friends or family provided comfort and relief. Examples of their responses include:

(Participant 9) "I like going for a run when I feel stressed. It clears my mind and gets rid of the heaviness I feel after sitting around doing schoolwork all day."

(Participant 12) "I go hiking or take a bike ride. Sometimes I just sit by a lake with a book or some music. It gives me space to breathe and makes a big difference."

(Participant 4) "I talk to friends when I'm stressed. We vent about school and everything that's overwhelming us. It's nice knowing we're all going through it together."

(Participant 3) "I usually share my worries with my parents. They listen and help me think through what's bothering me, which makes me feel a lot more grounded."

Students who consciously chose to engage in these activities used coping strategies that helped regulate and alleviate their emotions (Lazarus et al., 1984). However, these strategies mainly served as distractions rather than addressing the root causes of their distress. By focusing on physical recreation, entertainment, or social interactions, they shifted their attention away from their problems rather than actively working to resolve them.

Resolution

A third trend in the data was that students coped with stress by actively addressing its causes. During the interviews, they discussed strategies at both individual and collective levels, including making plans, organizing their time, practicing school tasks, adopting

positive thinking, and collaborating with others to find solutions. Their responses highlighted a proactive approach to managing stress. Examples include:

(Participant 8) “Whenever I am feeling stressed, I take my tasks and breakdown what I need to get done into a list of priorities. I feel greatly accomplished when I check tasks off the list, so I always start with the most important items. I try to tackle everything on my checklist, which gives me a sense of control over the situation. For me, this is a good habit because it limits the amount of stress that I have to deal with.”

(Participant 11) “Whenever schoolwork starts piling up, I make it a point to reach out to my classmates. After all, they are facing the same challenges so we can come together and think of solutions for our problems. It gives me comfort to know that I am not the only one who needs assistance.”

(Participant 7) “In the event that I do poorly on a test, my focus shifts to dissecting the cause that lead to the low grade. For example, if I scored poorly in an examination for math, I take time to analyze the questions on the test and redo them for my next preparations. This is not something easy, but it is useful in helping me progress.”

(Participant 5) “The first thing I do is change my mentality whenever I feel too stressed out. Rather than focusing on how overwhelming my tasks appear, I break everything down into smaller steps. I also tell myself that things are not as bad as they seem. Remaining positive allows me to avoid excessive amounts of anxiety.”

These responses show that students take deliberate steps to resolve their challenges. They actively organize tasks and structure their time, seek support from peers who understand their struggles, focus on self-improvement even when it’s difficult, and use cognitive strategies like positive thinking to maintain control. By addressing their stressors headon, they demonstrate a level of resilience and agency in managing their academic and emotional well-being.

IMPLICATIONS

This research lays the groundwork for future studies, to assist students and educational institutions in developing more coordinated and supportive academic programs. It highlights the need for further exploration of the relationship between students’ mental health and their coping strategies, which could inform targeted interventions to enhance student well-being. Additionally, while much research has focused on distress, there is a notable gap in studies examining eustress—the positive form of stress—and its potential benefits for university students’ academic success. Addressing this imbalance could provide valuable insights into how stress, when managed effectively, can foster growth and resilience among students.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study underscores the alarming rate of stress among students, and in particular English-majored students, who report academic stressors like examinations and volumetric load to be the most detrimental. It was established that elevated stress levels were amplified by the fear of failure as well as non-academic factors like limited free time and nostalgia for one’s home. While having provided some insights, the study has numerous caveats that need to be pointed out. For instance, lacking member checks in qualitative data validation might have caused important aspects of students’ coping mechanisms to be missed. Moreover, the findings are not automatically applicable to every setting considering the subjects were all students of a private university located in HCM city. Furthermore, the study does not address the role of coping strategies towards mental health, a fact that limits its ability to provide conclusive recommendations. What strengths the study does have come from the use of face-to-face interviews which provided an opportunity for greater interaction and understanding the students coping with the reality of their experiences. For now, there is a need for further research to understand the ways in which coping strategies transform over time and their relationship with one’s mental health and academic productivity.

REFERENCES

1. Aldao, A., Nolen-Hoeksema, S., & Schweizer, S. (2010). Emotion-regulation strategies across psychopathology: A meta-analytic review. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 30(2), 217–237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpr.2009.11.004>
2. Baker, S. R. (2003). A prospective longitudinal investigation of social problem-solving appraisals on adjustment to university, stress, health, and academic motivation and performance. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 35, 569–591.
3. Bandura A. (2001). Social cognitive theory: An agentic perspective. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 52, 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.52.1.1>

4. Bernold, L. E., Spurlin, J. E., & Anson, C. M. (2007). Understanding our students: A longitudinal-study of success and failure in engineering with implications for increased retention. *Journal of engineering education*, 96(3), 263-274.
5. Brinkmann, S., & Kvale, S. (2018). Doing interviews.
6. Brougham, R. R., Zail, C. M., Mendoza, C. M., & Miller, J. R. (2009). Stress, sex differences, and coping strategies among college students. *Current psychology*, 28, 85-97.
7. Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2022). Thematic analysis. A practical guide. Sage Publications.
8. Carver, C. S., Scheier, M. F., & Weintraub, J. K. (1989). Assessing coping strategies: a theoretically based approach. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 56(2), 267.
- Cheng, C., Lau, H. P., & Chan, M. P. (2014). Coping flexibility and psychological adjustment to stressful life changes: A meta-analytic review. *Psychological Bulletin*, 140(6), 1582–1607. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0037913>
9. Creswell, J. W. (2007). Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches (2nd ed.). Sage Publications, Inc.
10. Dahlin, M., Joneborg, N., & Runeson, B. (2005). Stress and depression among medical students: A cross-sectional study. *Medical education*, 39(6), 594-604.
11. DeBerard, M. S., Spielmann, G. I., & Julka, D. L. (2004). Predictors of academic achievement and retention among college freshmen: A longitudinal study. *College student journal*, 38(1), 66-81.
12. Fairbrother, K., & Warn, J. (2003). Workplace dimensions, stress and job satisfaction. *Journal of managerial psychology*, 18(1), 8-21.
13. Frydenberg, E., & Lewis, R. (1996). A replication study of the structure of the adolescent coping scale: Multiple forms and applications of a self-report inventory in a counselling and research context. *European Journal of Psychological Assessment*, 12(3), 224–235. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1015-5759.12.3.224>
14. Goldfinch, J., & Hughes, M. (2007). Skills, learning styles and success of first-year undergraduates. *Active learning in higher education*, 8(3), 259-273.
15. Högberg, B. (2021). Educational stressors and secular trends in school stress and mental health problems in adolescents. *Social Science & Medicine*, 270, 113616
16. Högberg, B., & Strandh, M. (2024). Temporal trends and inequalities in school-related stress in three cohorts in compulsory school in Sweden. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00313831.2024.2330932>
17. Jones, A., Smith, B., & Brown, C. (2021). Factors contributing to stress among students in an English Language Department: A comprehensive analysis. *Language Teaching Research Quarterly*, 35(2), 88106. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362168820989710>
18. Hilt, L. T., Søreide, G., Riese, H., & Bjørge, G. (2024). ‘School is the foundation of everything’: Master- and counter-narratives in lower secondary school pupils’ stories about the importance of schooling and education. *YOUNG*, 32(3). <https://doi.org/10.1177/11033088231221653>
19. Kato T. (2012). Development of the Coping Flexibility Scale: Evidence for the coping flexibility hypothesis. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 59(2), 262–273. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0027770>
20. Kohn, J. P., & Frazer, G. H. (1986). An academic stress scale: Identification and rated importance of academic stressors. *Psychological reports*, 59(2), 415-426.
21. Lazarus, R. S., & Folkman, S. (1984). *Stress, Appraisal, and Coping*. Springer Publishing Company.
22. Lee, H. J., Park, J., & Kim, S. (2023). Academic expectation stress, adaptive coping, and academic burnout among students in English learning programs: Interplay and implications. *BMC Psychology*, 11(1), 43. DOI: 10.1186/s40359-024-01630-y
23. Lumley, M. A., & Provenzano, K. M. (2003). Stress management through written emotional disclosure improves academic performance among college students with physical symptoms. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 95(3), 641.
24. Mani, V. (2010). Students’ perception of the impact of course work on exam stress. *International Journal of Arts and Sciences*, 3, 104-110.
25. Misra, R., & McKean, M. (2000). College students' academic stress and its relation to their anxiety, time management, and leisure satisfaction. *American Journal of Health Studies*, 16(1), 41–51.

26. Muema, E. N., Muola, J., & Muriungi, P. (2020). Relationship between perceived academic stress and academic performance among students in primary teacher training colleges in central region, Kenya.
27. Nguyen, H. T., Tran, L. P., & Dao, T. (2020). English-majored students and the stress of language proficiency: A case study at a Vietnamese university. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 11(4), 680-687. <https://doi.org/10.17507/jltr.1104.09>
28. Nowell, L. S., Norris, J. M., White, D. E., & Moules, N. J. (2017). Thematic analysis: Striving to meet the trustworthiness criteria. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 16, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1177/16094069177338>
29. Pascoe, M. C., Hetrick, S. E., & Parker, A. G. (2020). The impact of stress on students in secondary school and higher education. *International Journal of Adolescence and Youth*, 25(1), 104–112. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673843.2019.1596823>
30. Rajendran, R., & Kaliappan, K. V. (1990). Efficacy of behavioural programme in managing the academic stress and improving academic performance. *Journal of Personality and Clinical Studies*, 6, 193-196.
31. Saha, R., Huebner, E. S., Hills, K. J., Malone, P. S., & Valois, R. F. (2014). Social coping and life satisfaction in adolescents. *Social Indicators Research*, 115(1), 241–252. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-012-0217-3>
32. Skinner, E. A., Edge, K., Altman, J., & Sherwood, H. (2003). Searching for the structure of coping: A review and critique of category systems for classifying ways of coping. *Psychological Bulletin*, 129(2), 216–269. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.129.2.216>
33. Sinha, U. K., Sharma, V., & Nepal, M. K. (2001). Development of a scale for assessing academic stress: a preliminary report. *Journal of Institute of Medicine Nepal*, 23(1 & 2), 105-112.
34. Wang, Y., Chen, H., & Zhang, L. (2022). Linguistic students' academic stress and coping mechanisms: A systematic review. *International Journal of Linguistic Studies*, 8(4), 200–216.
35. Wang, Y., Zhang, X., Li, L., & Zhang, Q. (2022). The relationship between English learning stress and burnout among undergraduate students: The mediating role of self-efficacy and the moderating effect of mindfulness. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 114(3), 360-375. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000521>
36. Zeidner, M. (1992). Sources of academic stress: The case of first year Jewish and Arab college students in Israel. *Higher Education*, 24(1), 25-40.
37. Zimmer-Gembeck, M. J., & Skinner, E. A. (2016). The development of coping: Implications for psychopathology and resilience. *Developmental Psychopathology*, p. 1–61. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119125556.devpsy410>

Cite this Article: Dang, T.D.M.(2025). Exploring English-Majored Students' Academic Stress and Coping Strategies: A Mix Method Research at A Private University. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 8(2), pp. 894-903. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V8-i2-39>